

INTEGRATION OF LIQUID ORGANIC HYDROGEN CARRIER WITH SOLID OXIDE FUEL CELL AND WASTE HEAT RECOVERY SOLUTIONS FOR MARITIME USE

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ABSTRACT

Led by the need for decarbonizing the marine sector towards the target of zero – emission vessels, this work examines an integrated Liquid Organic Hydrogen Carrier (LOHC) – Solid Oxide Fuel Cell (SOFC) system, as an alternative to fossil fuel driven internal combustion engines. The process is simulated in the Aspen Plus software, with a primary focus on the SOFC, for which a dedicated model has been developed. A share of the SOFC waste heat is provided to the LOHC reactors to drive the dehydrogenation process at a temperature of over 300 °C, and the remaining waste heat is exploited for additional power production. The integrated process is simulated for a variable load, concluding to the overall system efficiency. The results show that the 1 MW SOFC system achieves an electrical efficiency up to 60.4% at low loads, while the overall system efficiency can reach up to 89% when waste heat recovery solutions based on Organic Rankine Cycle (ORC) technology are implemented to exploit two different waste heat sources at a temperature of 120 and 180 °C.

1 INTRODUCTION

The increasing need to reduce greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions from the shipping sector in order to comply with the regulations of IMO and of the European Union has led to the advancement of greener technologies. The EU aims to reduce the GHG emissions by 55% until 2030 and achieve climate neutrality by 2050 (UNEP, 2019). Currently, internal combustion engines (ICEs) are the main propulsion technology, utilizing fossil fuels such as marine diesel. However, alternative fuels like methanol, LNG and biodiesel are gradually being adopted to replace the conventional ones (Wallner and Miers, 2021). In the context of developing more sustainable solutions, hydrogen and fuel cell (FC) technology can be employed (Xing *et al.*, 2021). Fuel cells are electrochemical cells that convert the chemical energy of a fuel into electricity through redox reactions. Depending on the electrolyte substance, the fuel cells are divided into different types like Solid Oxide FC (SOFC), Proton Exchange Membrane FC (PEMFC), and Alkaline FC (Malik *et al.*, 2021). Especially the SOFC is probably the most promising FC type due to the potential of reaching very high conversion efficiency of even more than 55% (Stambouli and Traversa, 2002), while the high temperature heat at the exhaust can be used for various purposes (Kuchonthara *et al.*, 2003). A part of this heat is used for air and fuel preheating to enable the SOFC operation, and the remaining can be supplied to waste heat to power solutions for additional power production, such as a steam cycle, gas turbine (Kuchonthara *et al.*, 2003), (Rokni, 2010) or an Organic Rankine Cycle (ORC) (Al-Sulaiman *et al.*, 2010). Choi *et al.* (2019) conducted experiments and simulations regarding a Solid Oxide Fuel Cell (SOFC) – Internal Combustion Engine. In their study, an efficiency of 59% was demonstrated with near-zero CO and NO_x emissions. Nehter *et al.* (2017) developed a pilot scale diesel-SOFC (50 kW) for maritime applications that achieves a gross efficiency of 55% and reduces sulfur emissions to 11.3 ppm_{wt}. Fragiaco *et al.*, (2023) developed an

experimental scale SOFC (165 W), which uses compressed hydrogen and reformed carbon gases as anode fuel.

While hydrogen fuel cells offer a greener solution to conventional ICEs by eliminating CO₂ emissions, NO_x, and others, the conventional hydrogen storage and transportation technologies introduce significant safety and financial challenges, making the large scale implementation complex in marine vessels. Liquid organic hydrogen carriers (LOHC) on the other hand offer a viable alternative overcoming the limitations of liquid or compressed hydrogen. By the chemical bonding of hydrogen to liquid oil, this solution can offer enhanced safety, easy handling and high energy density (Van Rheenen *et al.*, 2023), releasing approximately 1.8 MWh/m³, while compressed hydrogen's volumetric energy density is equal to 1.34 MWh/m³.

In this study, a detailed electrochemical and thermal model of a SOFC is developed, in order to simulate 1 MW LOHC-SOFC system for maritime applications. A significant share of the available waste heat is supplied to the LOHC reactors, in order to drive the dehydrogenation process, reducing the temperature of the waste heat and imposing restrictions on the use of a steam cycle or gas turbine that typically require heat input at a temperature of over 250-300 °C. The performance of the system is evaluated under different load conditions, and its integration with ORC variants is examined in two configurations to enhance the total efficiency and demonstrate the main features of this technology.

2 METHODOLOGY

2.1 System description

The selected LOHC is perhydro-benzyltoluene (C₁₄H₂₀), which is a non-toxic, non-flammable liquid at standard temperature and pressure. Its volumetric storage capacity is 0.054 kg/L_{LOHC} (Modisha and Bessarabov, 2023), and it releases 6 moles of H₂ per mole LOHC during its dehydrogenation process typically occurring at a temperature above 280 °C. All processes of the complete system are integrated with the Aspen Plus software (AspenTech, 2024) and the produced flowsheet is presented in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Aspen Plus flowsheet of the LOHC-SOFC integrated process

The dehydrogenation reaction takes place in the vapor state at low pressure (2.4 bar) and high temperature in a catalytic environment. Preheating is first performed by the reactor outlet stream (mixture of dehydrogenated benzyltoluene BT-D, H₂ and unreacted BT-H) to about 295 °C (subcooled liquid state). The second heating step is performed by thermal oil, preheating and vaporizing the BT-H stream at 313 °C. The vapor BT-H is then divided into two separate streams that enter the two dehydrogenation reactors, with the flow rate of each stream determined by the initial flow rate and the system load. Under low load conditions, only one reactor is active, while the second reactor is put to operation for a load of over 50%. The reactors are maintained at a temperature of 313 °C, while the heat needed for the endothermic reaction as well as for keeping the temperature constant is provided by the

thermal oil. The thermal oil receives heat from the hot exhaust gases of the afterburner, where the combustion of the SOFC products takes place.

The dehydrogenated stream (H_2 , BT-D and the unreacted BT-H) after preheating the initial (liquid) LOHC stream, is cooled in two stages, so that the hydrogen is fully separated, as the BT-H / BT-D stream is condensed. The first cooling stage is achieved by a thermal oil cycle, which removes heat from the product stream until its temperature reaches 80 °C. The recovered heat can be utilized in a waste heat to power technology that operates at low temperature, such as an ORC, for further electric production. The thermal oil cycle (Figure 1) is simulated with a constant inlet temperature of 70 °C in HEX3 and an outlet temperature of 120 °C, with its mass flow rate adjusted accordingly. A typical water-cooled cycle is employed for the second cooling stage, which further decreases the temperature of the products to 15 °C. The specifications of the cooling water cycle include constant inlet and outlet temperatures in HEX4 (Figure 1) equal to 10 °C and 20 °C respectively, while the mass flow rate of the cooling water is varied to follow the system load.

The pure hydrogen after its two-stage separation (SEP and SEP2 in Figure 1) enters the SOFC along with compressed air (air to fuel equivalence ratio, $\lambda=2.7$), both of which are preheated by the exhaust gases of the afterburner, until the inlet temperature of the air reaches 500 °C. The hydrogen stream absorbs the rest of the heat of the exhaust gas stream. A typical pressure drop of 0.1 bar is considered at every heat exchanger, leading to the inlet streams of the fuel cell being at 2 bar pressure. The hot exhaust gases of the afterburner, after preheating both the thermal oil cycle and the fuel cell inlets, are discharged to the environment at a temperature up to 201 °C at maximum load. However, the utilization of their thermal content in a second ORC unit is also examined. It is important to mention that the maximum net power of the SOFC system reaches 1 MW, indicating that the gross electricity generated by the fuel cell is up to 1.12 MW, since the air compressor consumes up to 0.12 MW for the selected equivalence ratio that maximizes the system efficiency.

2.2 Process modeling

The steady-state simulation of the LOHC-SOFC process is implemented with Aspen Plus software (AspenTech, 2024), using built-in blocks, design specifications, and calculator blocks to model stream flows, pressure changes, heat exchangers, and the dehydrogenation reaction. The SOFC block is developed in Aspen Custom Modeler by coupling the electrochemical and thermal equations of the cell.

2.2.1 LOHC dehydrogenation: The BT-H stream is preheated in two stages before entering the reactors. In the first stage (HEX) heat transfer occurs between the reactant and product streams, with the cold (liquid) outlet specified to be subcooled by 10 K, resulting in an outlet temperature of 295 °C. The second stage involves an evaporator (HEX2), where the BT-H is vaporized with a superheat of 10 K. These setpoints are chosen to simulate a realistic system, ensuring that the phase change in the evaporator involves a subcooled liquid and superheated steam. The dehydrogenation of the LOHC takes place inside of two identical reactors (REACTOR1, REACTOR2) which are simulated with the RStoic block. The chemical reaction is described by Equation (1).

The reaction takes place in the vapor state at 2.4 bar and 313 °C. The degree of dehydrogenation (DoD) is given by Equation (2) and indicates the amount of hydrogen that is released ($\dot{n}_{BT-H_{out}}$) from the inlet flow ($\dot{n}_{BT-H_{in}}$) and it is calculated in a calculator block. Typical values of DoD are in the range of 40-80%, depending on the system's temperature and pressure (Willer *et al*, 2024).

$$DoD = \frac{\dot{n}_{BT-H_{in}} - \dot{n}_{BT-H_{out}}}{\dot{n}_{BT-H_{in}}} \cdot 100\% \quad (2)$$

2.2.2 SOFC model and validation: The SOFC consists of 3000 cells, with an area of 290 cm² per cell,

divided to 10 stacks. It was developed in the Aspen Custom Modeler software, coupling the electrochemical and thermal processes, in order to allow the estimation of the heat flows with good accuracy. The electrical power output, is calculated by Equation (3), while the electrical current, I , and voltage, V , are calculated by Equations (4) and (5) respectively.

$$P = V \times I \quad (3)$$

$$I = 2 \times F \times \dot{n}_{H_2,in} \quad (4)$$

$$V = V_N - V_{ohm} - V_{act} - V_{conc} \quad (5)$$

where F is the Faraday constant equal to 96485 C/mol, $\dot{n}_{H_2,in}$ is the inlet molar flow of H_2 , V_N is the Nernst voltage of the cell and V_{ohm} , V_{act} and V_{conc} are the ohmic, activation and concentration losses of the cell respectively according to Pianko-Oprych and Mateusz (2017) and Doherty *et al.* (2009).

A part of the initial hydrogen chemical energy is lost due to various losses (e.g. heat losses), equal to 1% of the power output (Becker *et al.*, 2012). The total energy balance is shown in Equation (6).

$$Q_{th} = U_f \times Q_{chem,in} - P - Q_{loss} \quad (6)$$

where Q_{th} is the change in enthalpy of the SOFC inlet and outlet, $Q_{chem,in}$ is the chemical energy of the hydrogen that enters the cell, U_f is the fuel utilization factor equal to 85% (Oryshchyn, 2018), P is the electrical power produced by the cells and Q_{loss} is the heat loss. $Q_{chem,in}$ is given by Equation (7).

$$Q_{chem,in} = \dot{n}_{H_2,in} \times LHV_{H_2,in} \quad (7)$$

where LHV_{H_2} is the lower heating value of hydrogen equal to 120 MJ/kg H_2 .

The (gross) electric efficiency of the SOFC and the net efficiency are described by Equations (8) and (9) respectively.

$$\eta_{SOFC} = \frac{P}{Q_{chem,in}} \cdot 100\% \quad (8)$$

$$\eta_{net} = \frac{P - W_{comp}}{Q_{chem,in}} \cdot 100\% \quad (9)$$

where W_{comp} is the power consumption of the air compressor.

The total efficiency is then defined by considering the additional power production of the WHR solutions and the heat provided to the dehydrogenation process, expressed by Equation (10).

$$\eta_{total} = \frac{P - W_{comp} + Q_{LOHC} + \dot{w}_{net}}{Q_{chem,in}} \cdot 100\% \quad (10)$$

where Q_{LOHC} is the heat supplied to the dehydrogenation process and \dot{w}_{net} is the net power production of the WHR solutions.

The validation of the SOFC model is based on experimental data from the literature and model results, both from Pianko-Oprych and Mateusz (2017), using the same fuel cell parameters and conditions (e.g. fuel cell temperature of 700 °C). The comparison of the polarization curve (voltage-current density) and the power density as a function of current density of the model output with the literature data are presented in Figure 2.

As observed in the polarization curve, increasing the current density up to 6000 A/m² leads to voltage drop. Up to 500 A/m² a rapid drop of the voltage curve would be expected, as a result of the activation loss. However, the developed model focuses on the FC operation at higher current densities, therefore

the disagreement to the literature data in this range is of minor importance. For larger current densities the linear decrease of the cell voltage is a result of the ohmic losses. On the other hand, the increase in current density leads to an increase in power density, as shown in Figure 2(b), reaching a peak at 6000 A/m². The model captures this behavior accurately, demonstrating its capability to predict SOFC performance under varying operating conditions.

Figure 2: Comparison of the SOFC (a) polarization curves and (b) current density against power density of the present model with literature data (Pianko-Oprych and Mateusz (2017))

2.2.3 Organic Rankine Cycle: An ORC system is considered to exploit the waste heat sources for additional power production. In the examined system, the low Global Warming Potential (GWP) refrigerant R1233zd(E) serves as the working fluid, due to its moderate pressure ratio and volumetric heating capacity, making it well-suited for a wide range of heating capacities and temperature lifts (Wu *et al.*, 2021). The refrigerant is evaporated at high pressure and temperature in the evaporator, utilizing the available waste heat from the fuel cell process. The high-pressure vapor is then expanded in an expander (simulated as a scroll expander), generating electricity. Subsequently, the low-pressure vapor is condensed using fresh seawater as the cooling medium and the cycle is completed by a pump, which increases the pressure of the low-temperature liquid refrigerant, preparing it for re-evaporation. To enhance system efficiency, a recuperator heat exchanger is incorporated (Park *et al.*, 2023). This component preheats the liquid refrigerant exiting the pump by recovering heat from the high-temperature stream at the outlet of the expander, reducing the load of the condenser.

Two waste heat sources are identified in the integrated process (Figure 1), feasible for ORC integration. The first one includes the oil stream from the cooling cycle at HEX3. This source is within a temperature range of 70–120 °C and exhibits a variable flow rate dependent on load conditions. The second one is the hot exhaust gases from the afterburner. These gases have a maximum temperature of around 200 °C and a variable flow rate. Heat from the exhaust gases is transferred to a secondary thermal oil circuit, which operates at temperatures up to 180 °C and delivers heat to the ORC evaporator. Based on these sources, a single or two ORC system configuration is considered, as shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3: Aspen Plus flowsheet of the developed ORC: (a) Single ORC system utilizing both waste heat sources, and (b) two ORC systems, one for each waste heat source

The single ORC configuration (Figure 3(a)) utilizes heat from the thermal oil circuit for preheating the liquid refrigerant, while the exhaust gas heat (via the secondary thermal oil circuit) is used for the boiling and superheating phases. On the other hand, the two ORC systems (Figure 3(b)) independently utilize the two identified waste heat sources. To assess the performance of the ORC, the key performance indicators are defined using Equations (11)–(13). The available waste heat \dot{Q}_{evap} (kW) that can be transferred to the working fluid in the ORC evaporator is calculated by Equation (11).

$$\dot{Q}_{evap} = \dot{m}_{htf} \cdot (h_{htf,in} - h_{htf,out}) \quad (11)$$

where \dot{m}_{htf} (kg/s) is the mass flow rate of the high-temperature waste heat source, while $h_{htf,in}$ (kJ/kg) and $h_{htf,out}$ (kJ/kg) are the specific enthalpies of the heat transfer fluid at the inlet and outlet of the heat exchanger, respectively. The net electricity output \dot{w}_{net} (kW) is determined by Equation (12).

$$\dot{w}_{net} = \dot{w}_{ex} - \dot{w}_{pu} \quad (12)$$

where \dot{w}_{ex} (kW) is the power generated by the expander, and \dot{w}_{pu} (kW) is the power consumed by the pump. The thermal efficiency η_{th} of the ORC is given by Equation (13).

$$\eta_{th} = \frac{\dot{w}_{net}}{\dot{Q}_{evap}} \quad (13)$$

The available waste heat from each source was determined based on the LOHC-SOFC process simulation. This includes the flow rates and temperatures of the thermal oil in the cooling cycle (HEX3) and the exhaust gas from the afterburner. Table 1 provides all the required parameters for solving the complete ORC system(s).

Table 1: Simulation parameters for the ORC

Component	Design Parameter	Value
Evaporator	Pinch Point	5 K
	Refrigerant superheat	5 K
Expander	Isentropic efficiency	Variable according to operating pressure ratio (PR). Equation from experimental data: $n_{is} = 0.0031 \cdot PR^3 - 0.0695 \cdot PR^2 + 0.4712 \cdot PR - 0.2937$ (-)
	Mechanical efficiency	0.98 (-)
	Condenser	Water inlet temperature
Condenser	Water temperature difference	5 K
	Refrigerant subcooling	2 K
	Pinch point	5 K
Pump	Efficiency	0.5 (-)
	Driver efficiency	0.97 (-)
Recuperator	Temperature change at the cold side	15 K
Preheater	Refrigerant subcooling	2 K
	Pinch point	5 K
Exhaust gas heat exchanger	Exhaust gas outlet temperature	140 °C
	Pinch Point	20 K

3 RESULTS

The integrated process is simulated for a variable load, ranging from 0.25 up to 1 MW of net power. The results initially focus on the SOFC, then on the ORC, and finally on the integrated system.

3.1. SOFC

The operating load has a significant effect on the dehydrogenation process, since one or both reactors operate also according to the inlet flow of the BT-H. The degree of dehydrogenation is depicted in Figure 4 (a) for a variable net power. The reaction conversion (DoD) ranges from 71% to almost 79%. For electrical power load in the range of 25% to 50% of the maximum, only one reactor operates, leading to a DoD of 75-79%. For a higher load than 50%, both reactors are activated, with the reaction conversion declining from 77% to 71% as the load reduces. On average, the DoD is around 75% (Willer *et al.*, 2024), with the remaining 25% of hydrogen still bonded in the BT-H flow and returning to a separate tank to be stored.

As previously mentioned, the dehydrogenation process requires significant amounts of heat and at a high temperature of more than 300 °C. A useful indicator is used here to describe the thermal energy required to the hydrogen released. This indicator, the specific heat demand, is given in Figure 4 (b) for a variable net power. This heat includes the required heat for the preheating of the BT-H stream, the heat of the reactor(s) and the enthalpy of reaction.

Figure 4: Effect of the SOFC net power on the (a) degree of dehydrogenation and (b) specific heat demand of the dehydrogenation process

The specific heat demand ranges from 11.5 to 11.7 kWh/kg-H₂, and increases for a higher net power. On the other hand, the DoD follows the reverse trend. In the extreme case of a DoD of 100%, the specific heat demand has the minimum value of 11.26 kWh/ kg-H₂, which reflects the operating condition closest to the ideal process.

Regarding the electric efficiency of the SOFC (Eq. (8)), the electrical current linearly increases (Eq. (4)) for higher inlet hydrogen flow, and so do the voltage losses of the cell (Eq. (5)), thus leading to smaller augmentation of the power output (Eq. (3)). Therefore, the higher hydrogen flow required to increase the load introduces efficiency losses, as depicted in Figure 5, which also gives the net efficiency once considering the power consumption of the air compressor.

Figure 5: Efficiency indicators for a variable SOFC net power

The electric efficiency decreases from 60.4% to 54.4% for load variation from 25% to 100%, while the net efficiency is about 5-6% less, ranging from 54.5% to 48.5%. Such efficiency values are typical for SOFC (Stambouli and Traversa, 2002), showing that they can be used in future applications as more efficient power blocks than internal combustion engines in the marine sector that show efficiency values typically below 45%. The exhaust gases of the SOFC contain 15% of the inlet hydrogen (according to the typical value of the utilization factor selected) and they enter an afterburner, where the remaining hydrogen is combusted to further lift the gas temperature up to 941 °C, as shown in Figure 6. These gases provide their thermal content to preheat the inlet compressed air and hydrogen and then to heat the thermal oil to drive the dehydrogenation process. The gas temperatures at different parts of the process (e.g. before being discharged to the environment or after heating the thermal oil for supplying with heat the ORC) are shown in Figure 6.

Figure 6: Gas temperatures for a variable net power

The outlet gas temperature is almost linearly correlated to the net power, implying that the available waste heat to the ORC increases for a higher load, as expected.

3.2 Waste heat recovery by the ORC

Regarding the integration of the ORC, when the oil cooling at HEX3 is selected as the heat source (first cooling process of the dehydrogenated LOHC), the available thermal energy supplied to the evaporator is about 94 kW with an inlet temperature of 120 °C, under full load conditions. In this case, the ORC achieves a maximum net electricity output of 7.4 kW, which corresponds to a thermal efficiency of 7.8%. However, due to the temperature restriction imposed by the oil circuit (a maximum outlet temperature of 70 °C), the pressure ratio of the selected working fluid remains relatively low, at approximately 3.8. This has a negative impact on both the thermal efficiency and electricity generation. When the second heat source of the exhaust gases is utilized, the gas temperatures reach approximately 200 °C, and the thermal oil up to 180 °C allowing for pressure ratios up to 9, significantly improving system performance. Under full load conditions, the available thermal power at the evaporator is 167.5 kW, resulting in a maximum net electricity output of 18.2 kW. The higher pressure ratios also lead to a notable improvement in thermal efficiency, which increases to 10.9%. To further improve the system, a configuration combining both heat sources was evaluated. In this case, part of the heat from the oil cooling circuit is utilized in a preheater, while the higher-temperature exhaust gas is employed for the evaporation and superheating phases. At full load conditions, this combined configuration provides in total 218.8 kW of thermal energy to the preheater and evaporator, resulting in a maximum net electricity output of 23.5 kW. This represents a 22.5% improvement in net electricity production compared to the exhaust gas-only case while maintaining about the same thermal efficiency.

Figure 7 (a) illustrates the variation in available thermal energy at the evaporator for a variable net power of the SOFC. When the oil cooling cycle is the sole heat source, the evaporator capacity ranges from 20 to 93.9 kW, corresponding to net electricity production between 1.8 and 7.4 kW, as shown in Figure 7 (b). For the exhaust gas-only case, the evaporator capacity varies from 8.24 to 167.6 kW, producing net electricity in the range of 1.0 to 18.2 kW. If these two heat sources are utilized in two discrete ORC systems, the total recoverable waste heat increases to 19.2 – 218.8 kW, depending on the SOFC net power, as depicted in Figure 7 (a). Consequently, the net electricity production ranges from

2.6 to 25.6 kW, as shown in Figure 7 (b). At full load conditions, this dual-ORC configuration achieves an 8.5 % increase in net electricity compared to the single ORC case with combined heat sources.

Figure 7: Variation of ORC (a) evaporator capacity, and (b) net electricity production as a function of the net power

However, it is important to note that the implementation of two discrete ORCs would significantly increase system costs. A detailed techno-economic analysis is therefore essential to assess whether the additional energy recovery justifies the higher investment, which is outside the scope of the current work.

3.3 Total efficiency

The ORC configurations produce additional electricity and thus improve the integrated system efficiency. It should be stressed here that due to the thermal requirements of the dehydrogenation process, the quantity/temperature of the available waste heat decreases and therefore does not allow to integrate alternative WHR solutions that are suitable for exploiting high-temperature heat, such as a steam cycle. At such conditions, the use of ORC solutions seems to be the most appropriate (Krieger *et al.*, 2016). The total efficiency of the system is depicted in Figure 8.

Figure 8: Total efficiency for variable net power

The results show that without the ORC, the system achieves the lowest efficiency, ranging from 83.4 to 88.7%. Depending on the heat source, the power production shows an improvement of up to 2%, with a maximum energy utilization of the integrated system up to 1873 kW. Once the dual ORC configuration is employed, the total efficiency reaches the highest value of 89%.

4 CONCLUSIONS

This study presents a comprehensive design and simulation of a 1 MW LOHC-SOFC system for maritime applications. The results demonstrate the feasibility of using perhydro-benzyltoluene (BT-H) as a hydrogen carrier, offering advantages in terms of safety, storage density, and system integration. The dehydrogenation process achieves conversion efficiencies ranging from 71 to 79%, with specific heat demands between 11.5 and 11.7 kWh/kg-H₂, ensuring an efficient hydrogen release process requiring reasonable amounts of heat to drive this process. A SOFC model has been developed in the Aspen Custom Modeler environment, coupling the electrochemical and thermal phenomena and properly validated. It has been incorporated in the integrated system with the processes included in Aspen Plus. The SOFC system exhibits an electric efficiency between 60.4% and 54.4%, with net system efficiency varying from 54.5% at partial load to 48.5% at full load. For maximum load the FC products exit at a temperature of 790 °C, the afterburner outlet gases reach 941 °C and after preheating the dehydrogenation cycle and the FC inlets, they are discharged to the environment at 201 °C. At this location they present an opportunity for further heat recovery through waste heat to power conversion technologies.

The integration of the ORC was analyzed for different heat sources, revealing that utilizing the exhaust gas as the primary heat source significantly improves system performance achieving a net electricity output of 18.2 kW with a thermal efficiency of 10.9% at full load conditions. A combined configuration using both the oil cooling circuit and exhaust gas further enhanced electricity production, providing 23.5 kW of net electricity while maintaining a similar thermal efficiency. However, a dual-ORC setup, which increases net electricity up to 25.6 kW, would significantly raise system costs, necessitating a detailed techno-economic assessment.

The total efficiency that includes heat supply to the dehydrogenation process and the ORC power production reaches a maximum of 89%, showing a 2% increase in efficiency in comparison to the system without the ORC solution.

Overall, the study confirms the viability of an LOHC-SOFC system as a clean energy solution for maritime applications, providing high efficiency and minimal environmental impact. Further research and optimization, particularly in the reactor design and heat recovery strategies, are needed to enhance the system performance and commercial feasibility in the future and accompanied with a techno-economic analysis to evaluate its cost-effectiveness.

NOMENCLATURE

DoD	Degree of dehydrogenation	(-)
F	Faraday constant	C/mol
I	electric current	A
LHV	lower heating value	MJ/kg
\dot{m}	mass flow	kg/s
\dot{n}	molar flow	kmol/s
P	electric power	W
Q	heat	W
U _f	fuel utilization factor	(-)
V	voltage	V
w	work	W

Greek characters

η	efficiency	(-)
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Abbreviations

FC	fuel cell
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htf	heat transfer fluid
ICE	internal combustion engine
LOHC	liquid organic hydrogen carrier
ORC	organic Rankine cycle
PEMFC	proton exchange membrane fuel cell
SOFC	solid oxide fuel cell
WHR	waste heat recovery

Subscript

act	activation
BT-H	benzyltoluene
chem	chemical
conc	concentration
evap	evaporation
ex	expander
H ₂	hydrogen
loss	loss
N	Nernst
net	net
pu	pump

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